

PARENTS' ENGAGEMENT IN HOME-BASED ACTIVITIES AND TEACHERS' EMOTIONAL AVAILABILITY: IMPLICATIONS ON KINDERGARTNERS' LEARNING SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the relationship between parents' engagement in home-based activities and teachers' emotional availability with kindergartners' learning skills. The study involved one hundred twenty (120) kindergartners aged 5 to 7 years old, along with their parents. The questionnaire underwent content validity and reliability to determine the internal consistency of the items being measured. The research employed a descriptive-correlational design, utilizing descriptive statistics and regression analysis to examine the relationships between the independent variables (parents' engagement and teachers' emotional availability) and the dependent variable (kindergartners' learning skills in terms of literacy and numeracy). The findings revealed that parents' engagement was generally moderate, suggesting room for improvement, while teachers' emotional availability was generally high, indicating a nurturing classroom environment. Kindergartners demonstrated proficiency in their learning skills. Both parents' engagement and teachers' emotional availability significantly influenced kindergartners' learning skills, with parents' engagement having the highest influence. The study highlights the importance of parental involvement and caring teacher-student relationships in fostering early academic success. The implications call for strengthening the home-school partnership and promoting caring relationships in early childhood education. By collaborating, parents, teachers, and schools can create a supportive environment that empowers kindergartners to thrive academically and socially.

Keywords: *parents' engagement, teachers' emotional availability, kindergartners' learning skills, early childhood education, home-school partnership*

INTRODUCTION

Within the early childhood education field, learning skills play a salient role in laying the foundation for the kindergarteners' academic and cognitive development. During these formative years, children are introduced to fundamental skills. According to World Bank (2018) education system in the Philippines is confronted with the challenge to make certain that students learn and improve their skills.

In the same vein, the overall result in 2019 of the National Assessment showed that many early grade learners are still having difficulty meeting the learning standards in early language, numeracy skills, and literacy skills. Hence, the Department of Education (DepEd) has issued Memorandum No. 173, series of 2019 entitled as HAMON: BAWAT BATA BUMABASA. The Department of Education is consistently carrying out its mandate to develop each student to be capable readers and responsible and productive citizens with the fundamental knowledge and abilities needed for lifetime learning.

Recently, the article released by Cristina Chi (2023) of Philstar Global emphasized that Filipino students are still among the least proficient in the world in the areas of math, reading, and science. This recent result was released by the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) in 2022, which was conducted by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). Accordingly, the nation's performance in 2018 did not significantly improve as measured by the most current test results.

In the school where the researcher is teaching, she observed in the assessment in reading and numeracy gathered in the Annual Status Education Report (ASER) tool that early graders have poor accomplishment levels in Math and as well as in English. This indicates that the learners have difficulty reading and comprehending English-written word problems in Mathematics. As such, they are unable to exhibit proficiency in these subject areas.

Bustos (2022) of the University of the Philippines emphasized the significance of raising K–3 pupils' reading and arithmetic proficiency, citing global tests that indicate Filipino students are falling behind their foreign peers. She felt that problems stemming from their subpar performance began at a young age. Therefore, it needs to be dealt with starting from preschool. Moreover, Pianta and Hamre in 2009 opined that high-quality instruction depends on the emotional support provided by teachers.

According to Fisher (2020), parents have the greatest impact on education, and one of the most crucial things parents can do to support their children's learning is to demonstrate to them the value of education (Sorbring and Lansford, 2019). As the study of Kim and Yu (2024) revealed, that children's reading and math scores were also favorably correlated with parents' engagement at home.

Parents' engagement in the early educational journey of their children plays a crucial role in a child's development. As observed by the researcher herself, many of the

parents could hardly give time for their young children because of some basic needs that parents must attend to, especially in the hinterland areas, where families have limited financial resources. Hence, this poses a challenge in providing educational support for their children.

Research Questions

This study determined the influence of parents' engagement in home-based activities and teacher's emotional availability in the kindergartners' learning skills of Southwest II District, Cagayan de Oro City Division for the school year 2023-2024.

Specifically, the study aimed to seek answers to the following problems:

1. What is the extent of parents' engagement in their kindergartners' home-based activities?
 2. What is the level of teachers' emotional availability in terms of:
 - 2.1 Sensitivity;
 - 2.2 Structuring;
 - 2.3 Non-intrusiveness; and
 - 2.4 Non-hostility?
 3. What is the level of the kindergartners' learning skills in terms of:
 - 3.1 Numeracy; and
 - 3.2 Literacy?
 4. Do the parents' engagement in home-based activities and teachers' emotional availability significantly influence the kindergartners' learning skills?
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METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design. Rodrigo et al. (2021) further explained that descriptive research seeks to provide an explanation for the current set of circumstances as a phenomenon, with researchers simply describing what is occurring or has occurred without direct control over the factors.

The study involved six (6) sections with a total of one hundred twenty (120) kindergartners aged 5 to 7 years old, along with their parents (1 parent per learner who also participated in the study). These kindergartners were enrolled in three (3) public schools in the southwest district of Cagayan de Oro City for the School Year 2023-2024. The researcher utilized a total enumeration approach, which means that all members of the population were included in the study.

The instruments that were utilized to collect data in this study was through a survey questionnaire. To ascertain the parents' engagement in home-based activities, the instruments of LeFevere (1996) on Parent's Engagement Assessment Questionnaire was modified to fit the context of the study which was answered by the parents. While for the teachers' emotional availability, the researcher modified the Emotional Availability

Teacher Questionnaire of Biringen's Emotional Availability (2011) which was answered by the kindergartners.

The researcher translated the questionnaires into mother tongue, the Sinugbuanong Binisaya, for it to be understood by the participants. Meanwhile, the learning skills were based from the Department of Education's Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCS) for kindergarten.

The researcher submitted all the research instruments to field experts and panel members for review and validation. After receiving their comments and suggestions, the researcher incorporated the feedback into the instruments to ensure their validity and appropriateness for the study.

RESULTS

Parents' engagement in the kindergartners' home-based activities was moderate, suggesting that there is room for improvement in parental involvement and support for their children's learning at home.

Teachers' emotional availability with their kindergartners was rated as high, implying that teachers are giving a nurturing and supportive environment helpful to the emotional development and well-being of the kindergartners.

Kindergartners demonstrated proficiency in their learning skills (literacy and numeracy skills), indicating that they have gained the necessary early knowledge and abilities to progress to move forward in their educational journey.

Parents' engagement in home-based activities and Teachers' emotional availability contributed to the variability of pupils' literacy, with parents' engagement as having a significant influence on the pupils' literacy.

Both parents' engagement and teachers' emotional availability significantly influence the pupils' numeracy with parents' engagement and non-hostility as having significant influence on the outcome variable when taken singularly.

Non-hostility as a dimension of teachers' emotional availability significantly predicts the kindergartners' numeracy skills.

DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of parents' engagement in their kindergartners' home-based activities. The data reveal that parents engage in their children's home-based activities to a moderate extent, as indicated by an overall mean of 3.43. This figure imply that parents are not always involved in their children's home-based activities, which may be attributed to the limited time they dedicate to their children, possibly due to the nature of their occupations. This is supported by the fact that 46 participants (38.33%) rated the extent of their engagement in their kindergartners' home-based activities as moderate.

Table 1

Frequency, Percentage and Mean Distribution of Parents' Engagement in their Kindergartners' Home-Based Activities

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High Extent	15	12.50
3.51-4.50	High Extent	40	33.33
2.51-3.50	Moderate Extent	46	38.33
1.51-2.50	Low Extent	15	12.50
1.00-1.50	Very Low Extent	4	3.33
	Total	120	100.0
	Overall Mean	3.43	
	Interpretation	Moderate Extent	
	SD	0.91	

Table 2 presents the summary of the components of teachers' emotional availability. The data indicate that teachers demonstrate a high level of emotional availability to their kindergartners, as evidenced by an overall mean of 4.17, interpreted as "high extent."

Table 2

Summary Table of Teachers' Emotional Availability

Components	M	Interpretation	SD
Sensitivity	3.29	Moderate Extent	0.36
Structuring	3.69	High Extent	0.44
Non-intrusiveness	3.99	High Extent	0.57
Non-hostility	4.17	High Extent	0.34
Overall	3.78	High Extent	0.29

Table 3 presents the summary table of kindergartners' learning skills in terms of literacy and numeracy. The data indicate that kindergartners have very good literacy skills, and outstanding numeracy skills. This finding suggests that the majority of

kindergartners have successfully acquired the necessary learning skills and are able to keep pace with the lessons provided by their teachers.

Table 3

Summary Table of Kindergartners' Learning Skills

Components	M	Interpretation	SD
Literacy	21.01	Very Good	7.02
Numeracy	17.03	Outstanding	4.80

Table 4 presents the regression analysis of the influence of parents' engagement in home-based activities and teachers' emotional availability on kindergartners learning skills in terms of literacy. Findings reveal that the whole model is significant ($F=7.78$, $p = .000$). Results further show that for every unit increase in their parents' engagement, there is a corresponding 3.69 increase in the kindergartners' learning skills in terms of literacy skills ($B=.3.69$, $t=5.49$, $p=.000$). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. Kindergartners whose parents get actively engaged in home-based activities also have higher learning skills in terms of literacy skills. It can be inferred that the more the parents engage themselves in the home-based activities of their kindergartners, the better are the literacy skills of their children.

Table 4

Regression Analysis of the Influence of Parents' Engagement and Teachers' Emotional Availability on Kindergartners' Learning Skills (Literacy)

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	
(Constant)	2.27	9.122		.249	.804
Parents' Engagement	3.69	.672	.479	5.49**	.000
Non-hostility	1.46	1.77	.070	.829	.409
Structuring	-1.50	1.44	-.094	-1.04	.301
Sensitivity	.956	1.70	.050	.561	.576
Non-intrusiveness	.589	1.17	.047	.501	.617
Model Summary					
R = .504	R ² = .254	Adjusted R ² = .222	F= 7.78**	p = .000	

Table 5 presents the regression analysis of the influence of parents' engagement in home-based activities and teachers' emotional availability on kindergartners' learning skills in terms of numeracy. Findings reveal that the whole model is significant ($F=16.25$, $p = .000$). Results further show that for every unit increase in their parents' engagement, there is a corresponding 3.201 increase in the kindergartners' learning skills in terms of numeracy skills ($B=.3.201$, $t=7.88$, $p=.000$) and also for every unit increase in teachers'

emotional availability in the non-hostility of teachers, there is a corresponding 2.78 increase in the kindergartners' learning skills in terms of numeracy skills ($B=2.78$, $t=2.61$, $p=.010$) Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. Kindergartners who view teachers who are non-hostile also have higher learning skills in terms of numeracy skills. It can be inferred that the combination of parents' engagement in home-based activities and teachers' emotional availability has increased the learnings of the kindergartners. Also, the more the parents engage themselves in home-based activities of their kindergartners and teachers who are non-hostile, the better will be the kindergartners' numeracy skills.

Table 5

Regression Analysis of the Influence of Parents' Engagement and Teachers' Emotional Availability on Kindergartners' Learning Skills (Numeracy)

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
(Constant)	-5.83	5.51			-1.06	.292
Parents' Engagement	3.201	.406	.608		7.88**	.000
Non-hostility	2.78	1.07	.196		2.61**	.010
Structuring	-.669	.871	-.061		-.768	.444
Sensitivity	1.37	1.03	.104		1.33	.187
Non-intrusiveness	-.439	.710	-.052		-.619	.537

Model Summary					
R = .645	R ² = .416	Adjusted R ² = .390	F= 16.25**	p = .000	

Conclusions

The study's findings have significant implications in the field of early childhood education, particularly in understanding the factors that contribute to the development of kindergartners' learning skills. The researcher's assumption that parents' engagement in home-based activities and teachers' emotional availability influence young learners' numeracy and literacy skills is supported by the results of the study. This assumption is grounded in the theoretical frameworks of Epstein's Parental Involvement Theory (1991) and Nel Noddings' Caring Theory (1984), which emphasize the importance of parental involvement and a caring educational environment in fostering children's learning and development. A supportive home environment plays a pivotal role in the development of the learning skills of young learners. Likewise, teachers who are non-hostile create an environment where cognitive development of learners is fostered.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. To the School Administrator, that they may create more programs on teaching parents on the techniques, strategies and activities that can be done at home;
 2. To the Kindergarten teachers, that they may undergo trainings that will enhance their capacity in dealing kindergartners;
 3. To the Parents, that they may provide more quality time for their children's learning skills; and
 4. To the Future Researchers, that they may utilize a bigger number of samples to widen conclusions of the findings and develop more comprehensive survey questionnaire on the teachers' emotional availability.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher obtained a certificate of approval from the school's Research Ethics Committee (REC) of Lourdes College to conduct the study. This approval ensured that the study adhered to ethical guidelines and protected the rights and well-being of the participants.

After receiving permission from the REC, the researcher sought approval from the school district's superintendent through the district supervisor. When the superintendent granted permission, the researcher approached the school principals and teachers to discuss the study and request for their cooperation.

The researcher then asked the class advisers to provide data on the learners' learning skills performance, which was used as part of the study's data collection process.

The researcher followed the three ethical tenets—respect for humans, beneficence, and justice according to the Belmont Report, Serpico (2024).

Participation in the survey was entirely voluntary, and the researcher ensured that all participants were fully informed about the study's purpose, procedures, and potential risks or benefits. For the kindergartners who participated in the survey on teachers' emotional availability, the researcher obtained informed assent, which was a simplified form of consent appropriate for young children. This assent was obtained in addition to the informed consent provided by the children's parents or legal guardians.

Parents who participated in the parental engagement in home-based activities questionnaire were given a consent form that clearly outlined the study's objectives, procedures, and any potential risks or benefits. The consent form also informed the parents that their participation was voluntary and that they had the right to withdraw from the study at any time without consequence.

Throughout the research process, the researcher maintained the utmost confidentiality relative to the data collected from the participants. This meant that the researcher stored the data securely, used it only for the intended research purposes, and did not disclose any identifying information about the participants to unauthorized individuals. The researcher also informed the participants about how their data were used, stored, and protected to ensure transparency and build trust.

By following these ethical guidelines and procedures, the researcher conducted the study in a manner that respected the rights and well-being of the participants while ensuring the integrity and reliability of the research findings.

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